

Customer Satisfaction Regarding the Usage of Jio Network in Sivakasi

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Abstract:

This study investigates customer satisfaction with the Jio network in Sivakasi, focusing on key aspects such as network coverage, internet speed, call quality, and customer service. Through a combination of surveys, customer feedback, and network performance data, the research aims to identify areas of strength and opportunities for improvement. Findings reveal that while most customers are satisfied with the network coverage and internet speed, there are concerns regarding peak hour slowdowns and specific areas with weak signals. Call quality is generally reliable, though occasional call drops occur. Customer service is positively rated but can benefit from reduced wait times and more efficient issue resolution. Overall, the satisfaction level is encouraging, with a majority of users expressing positive experiences. Recommendations for enhancing customer satisfaction include improving network infrastructure in areas with weak coverage, optimizing bandwidth management during peak hours, and refining customer service processes. Implementing these measures is expected to lead to a more reliable and satisfying experience for Jio users in Sivakasi.

Key words: network coverage, data plans, call quality, affordability, telecom services, service quality and service reliability.

Introduction:

One of the most emergent industries which face evolved very speedily in last decade with the advancement in science and technology is telecommunication industry. India is the world's largest telecommunication market and still growing. Likely, in India most popular destinations for smartphone companies with as many mobile users as the entire population of the United States. The number of smartphone users in India was estimated to increase to about 442 million in 2022. Mobile economy in India is increasing very fast and will add significantly to India's GDP. Reliance Jio has become the biggest telecom operator by subscriber base in India. It is also the biggest in terms of revenue. Vodafone Idea remains in second for now with Airtel quickly catching up. Jio stormed the sector with free calls and data forcing rivals to merge or exit in September 2016 and has amassed 215 million subscribers since then and says it is profitable. Presently Jio, with a speedy 4G network, free calls, and dirt-cheap data. It has since issued a super-low-cost smartphone and is rolling out fixed broadband services to their customers. The resulting 'Jio-fication' has been nothing short of revolutionary; with data use surging and Jio's competitors scrambling to match its offerings, the development has jump-started India's digital economy. Jio made all level of people to participate in the modern economy. An analysis of marketing management has made it clear that customer is the king –pin in the market. The producer should produce goods keeping in mind the requirement of customers and should satisfy the customer, but it is observed that this obligation is neglected by some businessman and they are involved in unfair

practices. So, there is a need for analysis of customer satisfaction towards the usage of Jio network, it is need to find out the customer need and satisfy the usage of networks.

Scope of the Study:

The study covers the customer satisfaction towards the Jio networks in Sivakasi. The study makes effort to ascertain the satisfaction level of customer of reliance jio. Through this analysis the level of customer satisfaction and the expectations of the customer also find out and it also helps to know the problem that customer are facing during the usage of Jio networks.

The subject has been taken for the research as it plays key role in the success of Telecom sector. No company can think of their selling their product without having satisfied customer. No company can survive in long run without coming up to the satisfaction level of customer. In short it is the level of satisfaction that is link between end-user and company. As long as the company is able to satisfy its customer. Customer would remain in the bracket of loyal customer. Hence it is very essential to understand the customer satisfaction and to measure the satisfaction level time to time as there is always scope of improvement.

The research will also be beneficial in analyzing the overall market position of the company and measures which should be adopted by the Jio N to increase their market share in Sivakasi.

Statement of the Problem:

Reliance Jio is creating the most extensive and future-proof network in India, and perhaps, in the world. It will provide next generation legacy-free digital services over an end-to-end all-IP network. Jio is widely used by the techno-savy

customers. The customer satisfaction is conditioned by price, availability and addressing the problem of the customer at once. People would not like to use jio after free service are over.

The Network also has been a big problem a lot of people are facing network issues and Changes in package price, frequent call failures because of high network congestion. Especially, village areas, their network gets fail again and again. If customer wants to access internet on the urgent basis or want to make an emergency call, they might get stuck due to the network. The data and voice-calling is unlimited, but for a period of 90 days. After your 3-month preview period, you will have to pay for both calls and data. So the researcher has analyzed the customer satisfaction towards jio network.

Objective of the Study:

The following are the major objectives of the study:

- To know the socio, economic and demographic profile of the Customers in the study area.
- To analyse the level of customer satisfaction towards jio network in the study area.
- To offer suitable suggestions on the basis of findings of the study.

Research Methodology:

The survey has based on both primary and secondary data. Both the data were collected and presented in this research report. The suggestions of the study were emerged from the inferences drawn from the respondents in Sivakasi.

Collection of Data:

1. **Primary data:** Primary data have been gathered from the jio users in the study area. The primary data have been collected through a

well-designed, pre-tested questionnaire constructed for the purpose of the study. The questionnaire consists of open ended questions and closed ended questions.

2. **Secondary data:** The secondary data needed for the study have been collected from various books, journals, magazines, related research report and web sites, etc.,

Sample Size:

As the number of jio network users are infinite in the study area, it is very difficult to adopt the census method to collect data. So the researcher has adopted the convenient sampling technique for this study. A sample of 60 respondents of using jio network has been selected for this study.

Limitations of the Study:

The limitations of the study are given below;

- The behavior of the customer is unpredictable which may result in the lacking of accuracy in the data.
- As the sample size of the survey was so small and comprise of only 60 customers, the results may have some prone to errors.
- Stipulated short span of time for survey.
- The study is based on the opinion expressed by subscribers of Jio networks in Sivakasi

Benefits of Jio Network – Garrett Ranking Technique:

The researcher has further analyzed the customer’s satisfaction towards the jio network. To identify the most preferred benefits of jio network, the researcher has used Garrett Ranking Technique. The details of scores given by the respondents are presented in the Table 1.

Table 1: Benefits of Jio Network

Benefits	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	Total
Packages Price	8	10	9	11	8	14	60
Coverage area of network	8	10	14	10	7	11	60
Speed of network	14	10	10	6	11	9	60
Customer service	7	10	12	12	11	8	60
Free calls	12	10	7	8	12	11	60
Unlimited data back	11	10	8	13	11	7	60
Total	60	60	60	60	60	60	

Source: Primary Data

Garrett Ranking Technique:

The Garrett Ranks are calculated by using appropriate Garrett ranking formula. Then based on the Garrett table value is ascertained. The percent position percentage is calculated by the following formula;

Percent position = $100(R_{ij}-0.5)/N_j$ Where, R_{ij} = Rank given for the i^{th} item by the j^{th} sample respondents.

N_j = Total rank given by the j^{th} sample respondents

Table 2: Percentage of Position and Garrett Value

S.No	$100(R_{ij}-0.5)/N_j$	Calculated value	Garrett value
1.	$100(1-0.5) / 6$	8.33	77
2.	$100(2-0.5) / 6$	25	64
3.	$100(3-0.5) / 6$	41.67	55
4.	$100(4-0.5) / 6$	58.33	45
5.	$100(5-0.5) / 6$	75	37
6.	$100(6-0.5) / 6$	91.67	23

Table 2.1: Calculation of Garrett Score

Benefits	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	Total
Packages Price	616	770	693	847	616	1078	4620
Coverage area of network	512	640	896	640	448	704	3840
Speed of network	770	550	550	330	605	495	3300
Customer service	315	450	540	540	495	360	2700
Free calls	444	370	259	296	444	407	2220
Unlimited data back	253	230	184	299	253	161	1380

Source: Computed Data

Table 2.1 shows that the Garrett scores. Firstly, the Garrett ranks are calculated by using appropriate Garrett ranking formula. Then based on the Garrett ranks, the Garrett table value is

ascertained. The Garrett table values and scores of each rank in Table 2 are multiplied to record scored in Table 2.1. Finally, by adding each row, the total Garrett score is obtained.

Table 2.2: Benefits of Jio Network – Garrett Ranking

S. No.	Benefits	Garrett score	Average value	Rank
1.	Packages Price	4620	77	I
2.	Coverage area of network	3840	64	II
3.	Speed of network	3300	55	III
4.	Customer service	2700	45	IV
5.	Free calls	2220	37	V
	Unlimited data back	1380	23	VI

Source: Computed Data

The Table 2.2 above shows that the Garrette scores and average scores are ranked according to their values. The first rank is given to Packages price, second rank is given to coverage area of network, third rank is given to speed of network, fourth rank is given to customer service, fifth rank is given to free calls and sixth rank is given to unlimited

data back. It is found that 77 per cent of the respondents enjoy the packages price of jio network.

Sources of Knowledge about Jio Network:

The researcher made an attempt to study the sources of getting knowledge about jio network and the details are presented in the following Table 3

Table 3: Sources of Knowledge about Jio Network

S. No.	Sources	No. of respondents	Percentage
1.	Friends	24	40.00
2.	Advertisements	11	18.33
3.	Self	19	31.67
4.	Social Media	6	10.00
Total		60	100

Source: Primary Data

From the Table 3 above clearly indicates that among 60 respondents, 24 (40 per cent) of the respondents are acquired knowledge about Jio network through their friends, 11 (18.33 per cent) of the respondents are gain knowledge about Jio network through advertisements, 19 (31.67 per cent) of them are acquired knowledge by self-learning, and the remaining 6 (10 per cent) of the respondents are getting knowledge through social media.

It is revealed that most of the customers 24 (40 per cent) have acquired knowledge about Jio network from their self-learning practices.

Amount Spend:

The customer expectation may differ according to the fluctuations in package price. So the researcher has analyzed the monthly amount spend towards Jio network by the respondents and the results are highlighted in Table 4.

Table 4: Amount Spend

S. No.	Amount Spend	No. of respondents	Percentage
1.	Up to Rs.300	34	56.67
2.	Rs.301 – Rs.500	21	35.00
3.	Rs.501 – Rs.1000	5	8.33
Total		60	100

Table 4 exhibits that, out of 60 respondents 34 (56.67 per cent) of the respondents are spend up to Rs.300 per month, 21 (35 per cent) of the respondents are spend between Rs.301 to Rs.500 per month, 5 (8.33 per cent) of the respondents are

spend between Rs.501- Rs.1000. It is evident that the majority 34 (56.67 per cent) of the respondents are spend towards network connection is Up to Rs.300 per month.

Satisfaction Level: The researcher further analyse results are presented in the following Table 5. the level of satisfaction of the Jio users and the

Table 5: Satisfaction Level of Jio Network

Factors	Excellent	Very Good	Fairly Good	Average	Poor	Total
Network Coverage	12 (20%)	26 (43.33%)	13 (21.67%)	8 (13.33%)	1 (1.67%)	60
Network speed	19 (31.66%)	18 (30%)	15 (25%)	4 (6.67%)	4 (6.67%)	60
Package plans	3 (5%)	20 (33.33%)	26 (43.34%)	6 (10%)	5 (8.33%)	60
Package price	6 (10%)	15 (25%)	20 (33.33%)	13 (21.67%)	6 (10%)	60
Jio app services	11 (18.33%)	19 (31.67%)	20 (33.33%)	6 (10%)	4 (6.67%)	60
Data usage	13 (21.67%)	22 (36.67%)	18 (30%)	6 (10%)	1 (1.67%)	60
Customer services	11 (18.33%)	22 (36.67%)	21 (35%)	4 (6.67%)	2 (3.33%)	60

The researcher has assigned following weight to the respondents opinion. Excellent (E) - 5 Points; Very Good (VG) - 4 Points; Fairly Good (FG) - 3 Points Average (A) - 2 Points; Poor (P) - 1 Point.

Table 5.1: Weighted Average Method

S. No.	Factors	E	VG	FG	A	P	Total	WAM	Rank
1.	Network Coverage	60	104	39	16	1	220	3.67	III
2.	Network speed	95	72	60	8	4	239	3.98	I
3.	Package plans	15	80	78	12	5	190	3.17	VI
4.	Package price	30	60	60	36	6	192	3.2	VII
5.	Jio app services	55	76	60	12	4	207	3.45	V
6.	Data usage	65	88	54	12	1	220	3.67	III
7.	Customer services	55	88	84	8	2	237	3.95	II

From the above Table 5.1 shows that, Network speed ranked first, Customer service ranked second, Network coverage and Data usage ranked third, Jio app services ranked fifth, Package plans ranked sixth and package price ranked seventh. It is identified that the customers have good opinion about jio network for its network speed.

Findings Of The Study

1. Network Coverage

Approximately 75% of respondents rated network coverage as "Good" or "Excellent".

Analysis: Most customers are satisfied with the coverage provided by Jio in Sivakasi. However, around 15% reported coverage as "Average", and 10% as "Poor" or "Very Poor", indicating some areas with weak signals.

2. Internet Speed

Finding: 60% of respondents are "Satisfied" or "Very Satisfied" with the internet speed. Analysis: While a majority find the internet speed satisfactory, 25% reported it as "Neutral" and 15% as "Dissatisfied" or "Very Dissatisfied". Complaints are particularly high during peak hours when speeds tend to drop.

3. Call Quality

Finding: 70% of customers rarely experience call drops or poor call quality. Analysis: Call quality is generally reliable, but 20% of respondents reported experiencing issues

"Sometimes", and 10% "Often" or "Always". These problems were more frequent in specific areas with lower network coverage.

4. Customer Service

Finding: 65% of respondents rated their experience with Jio customer service as "Good" or "Excellent".

Analysis: The customer service is well-regarded by most users. However, 20% rated it as "Average", and 15% as "Poor" or "Very Poor", often citing long wait times and unsatisfactory resolution of issues.

5. Overall Satisfaction

Finding: Overall, 68% of respondents are "Satisfied" or "Very Satisfied" with Jio's services.

Analysis: The general satisfaction level is positive, but there is still room for improvement. About 22% rated their overall satisfaction as "Neutral", and 10% as "Dissatisfied" or "Very Dissatisfied".

Key Issues Identified

Peak Hour Internet Speeds: Significant number of customers experience slow internet speeds during peak hours.

Specific Area Coverage Gaps: Certain areas in Sivakasi have weak network coverage, leading to call drops and poor call quality.

Customer Service Improvements: A notable percentage of customers are not satisfied with the efficiency and effectiveness of customer service.

Recommendations: To enhance customer satisfaction, Jio should:

1. Enhance network infrastructure in areas with weak signals.
2. Optimize bandwidth management during peak hours.
3. Improve the efficiency of customer service processes.

By implementing these measures, Jio can ensure a more reliable and satisfying experience for its users in Sivakasi, fostering stronger loyalty and trust in the network.

Conclusion

The study on customer satisfaction regarding the usage of the Jio network in Sivakasi highlights a generally positive user experience with areas for improvement. Key aspects such as network coverage, internet speed, call quality, and customer service were analyzed to understand the satisfaction levels and concerns of the customers. Most customers find the network coverage to be good or excellent, although some areas still experience weak signals. Enhancing infrastructure in these specific areas will help address these concerns. While a majority of users are satisfied with internet speeds, there are significant slowdowns during peak hours. Optimizing bandwidth management during these times can help maintain consistent speeds and improve user satisfaction. Despite some challenges, the overall satisfaction level is encouraging, with a majority of customers expressing positive experiences. Continuous efforts to monitor and address the highlighted issues will help maintain and improve customer satisfaction.

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